

netWorked Youth Research for **Empowerment** in the Digital society

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Second Networking report

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1. WP4 Objectives

The WYRED project (García-Peñalvo, 2016b, 2017; García-Peñalvo & Kearney, 2016; Griffiths et al., 2017) and in this specific case the Networking process aims in bringing together children, young people, other stakeholders and policy makers from around Europe. That means that certain processes should be implemented in order to reach the objectives of the Networking Process:

- Build synergies and include a variety of different constituencies of stakeholders (including children and young people);
- Include and engage a sufficient critical mass of participants from diverse background in line with Working Package 2 (WP2) on Inclusion and Diversity;
- Initiate the process of dialogue in the project and foster engagement for further processes like Social Dialogue (WP5);
- Identify the key themes that concern children and young people in relation to future social change and prepare for future activities of WYRED cycle (WYRED Consortium, 2017a, 2017b);
- Attract participants through the process, that can engage on ongoing and future processes of WYRED project.

Each objective connects to a specific phase or set of processes that are expected to be applied in every WYRED Cycle, through the lifetime of the project.

2. The WYRED Network - Year 2

Over the course of the project, WYRED Consortium has been building the network of stakeholders and collaborators by promoting the idea behind it. More importantly, Consortium has paid significant attention to raising awareness about the project and the idea behind it to variety of stakeholders of different backgrounds with specific attention given to, naturally, young people and children as main stakeholders.

By involving different types of stakeholders – organisations, institutions and young people and children, WYRED Consortium is creating various interactions and connections with the main goal – to engage young people and children and create conditions to have their voices raised and listened to by decision makers and those who usually interact with them (civil society).

Additionally, Consortium is aiming at creating more direct links with decision and policy makers, especially in the light of the upcoming EU elections in May 2019. Some of these interactions already happened during the WYRED project and are described in more details below.

Having always in mind that WYRED Working Package (WP) 4 is a continuous process, we are presenting the achievements in the period between M7 and M24. As more young people and children, but also institutions and organisations are joining WYRED process, the project itself is growing and developing and, at the same time changing due to variety of interactions created.

This report is focusing on the following:

- **The WYRED Manifesto consultations:** Consortium with YEU as the leader of WP4, based on recommendations from the Technical Review Report has conducted consultations with young people all over Europe regarding Manifesto and its messages.
- **European Youth Event:** WYRED project representatives from Spain, Turkey, Belgium and Austria have organised a panel discussion and a workshop in European Parliament in Strasbourg as part of European Youth Event (EYE) in June 2018
- **Mapping out the institutional stakeholders:** Consortium has mapped out stakeholders to be approached for further cooperation and synergies with existing initiatives that could be valuable for the idea and topics that WYRED is working on.
- **Creating WYRED narrative – approaching young people:** based on the results of ongoing processes, WYRED Consortium has created a Working Group developing WYRED narrative with the idea to make WYRED more appealing and understandable to young people.
- **Delphi 02 research:** Consortium member – TAU has conducted second cycle of Delphi research reaching out to 987 young people and setting grounds for further discussions, research and cycle 03 process (Hauptman, Kearney, Raan, & Soffer, 2018).

2.1 The WYRED Manifesto process

During 2017, WYRED Consortium has, based on the input of young people created the first WYRED Manifesto setting the grounds for discussion and further development of the document that has been foreseen as a starting point in approaching young people and children to join WYRED. As the communities kept growing and gathering more and more young people of diverse age and backgrounds – cultural, socio-economical, religious, sexual orientation – the need to revise the Manifesto was becoming obvious.

Following the Technical Review Report made by Karen Triquet and Simon Schnetzer on January 24th 2018, WYRED Consortium has decided to consult young people about their needs, thoughts and opinions with a specific emphasis on digital society. YEU as the leader of WP4, supported by partners such as OXFAM, has created a set of 5 questions for young people with the idea to keep it simple but with open questions giving them the opportunity to express themselves freely.

The questions were:

What would you demand as a young person from stakeholders for a better digital society?

What are your biggest concerns regarding the digital society?

Do you feel that your voice is heard by decision makers? How would you change it or improve it?

What values should we have when being online?

What is the difference between digital and “real-life” society?

Process

Main part of consultations has been conducted during University on Youth and Development (UYD) in September (10-14th) 2018 in Mollina, Spain where 180 young people aged 15-30, of different backgrounds and coming from different parts of Europe gathered to attend one of 8 activities on different topics related to “Promote peaceful and inclusive societies organised by North-South Centre of Council of Europe.”¹

YEU has organised consultations in public premises of the CEULAJ campus (venue of UYD) where young people could anonymously answer the questions listed above by adding their answers on posts its or putting them in envelopes. In cooperation with other activity leaders in UYD, each activity has organised a 90 minutes session with young people discussing the questions. As an option, YEU has left it to activity leaders to decide with young people if they will be consulting the previous version of the WYRED Manifesto or not.

The activity leaders and young people were taking part on behalf of following youth organisations: National Youth Council of Portugal (CNJ), Young European Federalists (JEF), European Students Forum (AEGEE), European Association of High School Student Unions (OBESSU), Association of

¹ <https://www.coe.int/en/web/north-south-centre/-/call-for-activities-for-the-19th-university-on-youth-and-development-uyd->, visited October 28th 2018

Young Socialists (IUSY). YEU activity has gathered young people from 11 different organisations working in 11 different countries.

Methodology used for consultations was mostly based on non-formal education and different methods were used, mostly brainstorming where young people had opportunity to express freely their opinions on the topics listed above.

During September 2018, YEU has additionally consulted 50 young people from 24 different European countries during two-week events organised with Erasmus Student Network (ESN) in Slovenia. Process and methodology were similar to the process done in UYD – 90 minutes brainstorming sessions plus anonymous contributions by adding their answers on posts its or adding them into envelopes.

Other Consortium members have conducted consultations regarding the Manifesto in different settings and contexts, such as in informal discussions with young people. Overall, around 300 young people were consulted directly in face to face meetings and gatherings.

Results

The WYRED Manifesto consultations have gathered very interesting insights from young people on topics related to digital society. Although their reactions and statements might seem strong at times, they reflect a young person of today – willing to learn, to be free but “bombed” with overwhelming amount of information, short attention span and concerned with data protection and terms and conditions difficult to understand. Certain level of fear and anger is easy to notice. These young people strongly believe their voices are not heard and that politicians and decision makers keep forgetting to listen to them and their needs.

Some of the extracted statements from the first round of consultations are:

“Be positive! We need to show more respect by not just writing bad comments without real reasons, but also by giving some advices for better content.

When we are online we shouldn't forget that we are talking to a real person. Internet is not for hate speech.

Listen to our voices always, not only when you need us!

I think nobody is listening to us. Decision makers need to use more digital tools and platforms for feedback.

*I want to know what data they can collect and share. Terms and conditions are ununderstandable.
If we are only shown what we are already interested in.... how do we learn about other things? What if our interests change?*

Anonymity is sometimes good, but honesty and being yourself is better.”

After face to face consultations, WYRED Consortium has analysed the results of Delphi2 cycle questionnaire and its full text results (Appendix 2 of Delphi2) where we have found numerous similarities in opinions expressed by young people who took part in the questionnaire, especially related to question: “Internet safety and privacy-what should young people/stakeholders do to cope with these issues?” while other questions related to self-image, mental wellbeing and tolerance towards other cultures also offered very interesting perspectives.

Some of the extracted statements from the Delphi2 research are:

“Privacy doesn’t matter much, because it seems like we don’t have any.

We feel like we are being watched and listened to, even when we are told that we aren’t. What if in the near future, internet and technology will know what we want before we do?

Listen to us when you ask about our opinions and do it without prejudice - no point in asking if nothing is done about it.

Internet is not a place for hate and lies but for keeping us connected, informed and human, where we can feel safe, wanted and valued.

Educating on the values of mutual respect, tolerance and human dialogue, will support in solving the root problems and be more effective than treating the consequences. “

Based on inputs from consultations and Delphi2 answers, Manifesto has gained a different structure:

Our WORLD now: describes the situation as seen by young people and shares their concerns over decision making, society being acceptive of and understanding young people's heterogeneity and diversity

Our WORLD as we want it: young people are claiming their rights to be heard and to create the societies reflecting their different realities and identities

Our WORLD – what will we do to make it better: this part of Manifesto is a pledge to be proactive and not passive consumers by among others, claiming digital spaces as meeting points to discuss and call upon actions.

Calling upon stakeholders: this part defines the objectives of Manifesto and expectations of young people towards stakeholders.

Two versions of Manifesto

Due to the fact that young people are a very heterogenous group – regarding backgrounds, age, interests, Consortium has decided to create two versions of Manifesto – one longer that represents collection of young people’s thoughts related to digital society and issues they are facing in relation to it and one shorter that aims to attract younger people and children with simpler language (terminology) with basic information and requests towards stakeholders.

Full version of Manifesto contains the full text and several outlined statements with more detailed requests towards decision makers and stakeholders.

IN WYRED WE WANT TO
MAKE OUR VOICES LOUDER
EXPLORE THE THINGS THAT MATTER
UNDERSTAND OUR DIGITAL WORLD BETTER
AND
TELL THE PEOPLE IN POWER

Manifesto – full version is attached as Annex 1.

Manifesto – short version is attached as Annex 2.

2.2. European Youth Event

WYRED project representatives from Spain, Turkey, Belgium and Austria have organised a panel discussion and a workshop in European Parliament in Strasbourg as part of European Youth Event (EYE) in June 2018.

The third edition of the European Youth Event (EYE2018) took place on June 1-2nd 2018 with 8970 young people from all over Europe, with over 250 speakers, 11 partners and hundreds of youth organisations. Young people came from all 28 Member States plus countries from outside of EU, making a total of 109 nationalities present at the event.

The aim of the event was to give a platform to young active citizens to debate their ideas with Europe's decision makers with attendance of the President of the European Parliament, Antonio Tajani opening the event and attending the activities.

EYE2018 had 5 topics covered as part of the programme:²

1) YOUNG AND OLD: Keeping up with the digital revolution. Digital skills are required for so many jobs on the labour market. Although young people already possess great digital skills, Europe is investing heavily to create a single digital market and ensure that high-speed internet is available for all, leaving no one behind due to a lack of training.

2) RICH AND POOR: Calling for a fair share. Your fresh ideas on how to ensure that the world's scarce resources are more fairly distributed across Europe's single market are needed more than ever. If we want globalisation to bring benefits to all we need to make democratic choices to ensure social justice. Europe is a diverse continent and great economic disparities still remain.

3) APART AND TOGETHER: Working out for a stronger Europe. The European Union is undoubtedly a champion of peace and prosperity - we have a proud history and a great future ahead of us. However, Europe does not always speak with one voice. Are we punching below our weight? – Should we not be more ambitious?

² http://www.epgencms.europarl.europa.eu/cmsdata/upload/6f1c6e3e-d752-43bb-b0b8-7b054a088acd/A5_EYE_Programme_EN2018_V27.pdf, European Parliament, page 5, retrieved October 26th 2018

4) SAFE AND DANGEROUS: Staying alive in turbulent times. One of the greatest responsibilities for any government is to keep its citizens safe. European values have not been undermined by terrorist attacks, they have brought us closer together. However, the threat is evolving, from bombs to cyber-attacks, Europe's defenses are facing brand new challenges and finding innovative solutions is fundamental.

5) LOCAL AND GLOBAL: Protecting our planet. Young people will inherit our precious planet and Europe has been at the forefront of tackling climate for decades. The Paris Agreement is the foundation for protecting Earth, but some are ignoring the voices of scientists. This is the time to step up our efforts - there is a strong sense of urgency to fight the risk of climate collapse for the next generation. More about EYE2018 can be found in the official programme and report³.

WYRED at EYE2018

YEU has, on behalf of the WYRED Consortium, organized two activities as part of EYE2018, both part of the programme YOUNG AND OLD: Keeping up with the digital revolution:

- Panel discussion **Growing up in a digital society:** What matters most to young people?
- Workshop: **The digital revolution continues:** What will be the next steps?

³ http://www.epgencms.europarl.europa.eu/cmsdata/upload/d5f630ff-d0e6-49bf-8b20-6d921b94f7a0/EYE2018_report_EN_web.pdf, Publications Office of the European Union, 2018

Panel discussion Growing up in a digital society: What matters most to young people?

Growing up in a digital society: What matters most to young people?

Today's young people have grown up in a digital world, but they rarely get a say on what matters most in our digital society and what our priorities should be. Their world has been shaped, and is still being shaped, by others. Instead of being seen as passive objects of others' decisions, young people should be fully included in conversations on their own future. What do you think is the most important issue in our digital society? Join this discussion with experts and policy-makers and come up with solutions to these issues together.

Day, Time: Saturday, 14:00-15:00

Venue: LOW N 4.3, 70 places

Language: EN

Discussion

Organised by Youth for Exchange and Understanding

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YEU has organised a panel discussion in European Parliament in Strasbourg with MEPs Ms Terry Reintke and Mr Brando Benifei, European Youth Forum - Ms Mari Strømsvåg, Board member; Youth for Exchange and Understanding - Matej Manevski with following topics:

Europe and Digital Society - what is the status quo in European, National and Local level (based on their expertise);

The importance of engaging young people in decision making, specific focus on the topic of Digital Society and relevant processes;

How can we foster a dialogue between young people and stakeholders?

How can we create a connection and minimise the gap between decision makers and people?

How can we include their topics of interest, ideas and concerns in this dialogue and in the end in decision making (focusing mainly on issue of the digital society)?

The panel gathered approximately 60 young people and has been broadcasted on Facebook. For most of young people present, this was their first encounter with decision makers. YEU has targeted younger MEPs due to higher chances that young people will be able to relate to them due to age and terminology

they are using and that is closer to young people. During the panel, WYRED Manifesto and project were presented and served as basis for the discussion. Discussion showed very close correlation to “real-life” and for participants and speakers it was difficult to distinguish the differences between digital and real-life society as for them – it is one society.

Workshop: The digital revolution continues: What will be the next steps?

The digital revolution continues: What will be the next steps?

Young people have been navigating the digital society from an early age and technology has always played a prominent role in their lives. As such, their voices should be represented in discussions on how this society should evolve. What do you think are the most important changes we need to implement in the future? How do you envision the ideal digital society? Join us to discuss with other young people, design your own plan and become an active participant in the digital revolution!

Workshop

Organised by Youth for Exchange and Understanding (YEU)

Day, Time: Friday, 15:00-16:30

Venue: Yo!Fest Village, Digital revolution tent, 50 places

Language: EN

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This workshop has been organised with a topic: The digital revolution continues: what will be the next steps? with Ms Angeliki Dedopoulou, Policy Adviser in DG Employment, social affairs and inclusion as the main speaker. Main goals of the workshop were:

- Empower Young people and promote their engagement in decision making processes on Digital Society Issues and its' evolution;
- Acknowledge the benefits and the risks of the Digital Society;
- Engaging to shape the necessary changes that need to be implement in the future.
- Introduction to European Tools like ESCO that people can use to boost their CVs.

The workshop allowed us to use more non-formal education methodologies when discussing digital society related issues and how to get involved. During the workshop, YEU has presented WYRED platform (García-Holgado & García-Peñalvo, 2018; García-Peñalvo, 2016a; García-Peñalvo & Durán-Escudero, 2017; García-Peñalvo, García-Holgado, Vázquez-Ingelmo, & Seoane-Pardo, 2018) as a tool where young people can get involved, discuss and research.

2.3. Interactions with stakeholders on European level

Year 2 of WYRED WP4 building the network efforts have been increasing in the second part of 2018.

After successful participation and contributions at EYE2018, WYRED consortium has organised a Facebook live session with MEP Brando Benifei on July 10th with 4196 interactions online. Discussion with active participation of young people through Facebook comments has been organised and led by WYRED partner – YEU and topics were related to digital society and its influence on young people's life with specific emphasis on interaction with policy makers. The whole discussion with MEP Benifei can be found at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tuVXu34yL8w>

During University on Youth and Development (UYD) YEU has conducted an interview with Luis Alvarado Martinez, president of European Youth Forum (YFJ) on the topic of Empowering young people in digital society: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=O2lz938ylsw>. Topics of the interview were related to digital society and how young people can interact better with policy and decision makers.

Ongoing interactions and networking

European Youth Forum (YFJ) is the biggest advocacy platform of youth led organisations in the world and WYRED Consortium will further create closer relations with YFJ, specifically regarding the advocacy efforts regarding inclusion of young people and youth organisations in defining the priorities important for young people through consultations, Structured Dialogue, process of creation of new EU Youth Strategy, policy developments regarding Erasmus plus successor programme but also Digital Europe – upcoming programme of EU. Aims of such advocacy actions and synergies will be having young people's opinions considered, even potentially co-management system implementation on EU level and mainstreaming youth issues and including youth organisations in all EU programmes.

WYRED Consortium will create synergies with members of Lifelong Learning Platform and its members working on digital society issues through taking part in Working Group on Digital Learning and Media Literacy.

Example of topics covered within the Working Group on Digital Learning and Media Literacy:

**DIGITAL LEARNING & MEDIA LITERACY
 WORKING GROUP MEETING**

23 October 2018 - 14.00-17.00

AGENDA

Arrival and meeting point (Mundo J, Rue de l'Industrie 10) (getting to European Schoolnet for the visit)	14:00
Study visit: European Schoolnet Future Classroom Lab	14.30
Welcome words by Laurentiu Bunescu, Steering Committee Member of LLLP	15:30
<p>Updates from LLLP: ET2020 DELTA Working Group</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Key messages from mandate 2016-2018 ● New mandate & future priorities <p>Brainstorming</p> <p>a) <i>General updates from members</i></p> <p>b) <i>Discussing the 2 years work plan</i></p> <p>c) <i>Possible topics to address over the next 2 years (see below suggestions)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Media literacy ● Learning innovation ● Digital infrastructure in education ● Implementation of Digital Education Action Plan - how can CSOs contribute and monitor its implementation? ● Digital Competence Framework (DigComp) - how to use and raise awareness of the Framework? <p>d) <i>Working Group output</i></p> <p>e) <i>Project ideas & possible collaboration</i></p> <p>Conclusions and next steps</p>	<p>15:30</p> <p>17:00</p>

2.4. Mapping out stakeholders

WYRED Consortium, coordinated by OXFAM has created a non-exhaustive list of stakeholders mapped by each member of the Consortium. The ultimate objective of this document is to bring together relevant actors addressing the same target-group and issues, such as digital society, children and youth voices, at both national and international levels, in order to find new opportunities to undertake joint actions, exploit synergies and better improve our work. It will be the base of WYRED's stakeholder engagement strategy and will, in addition, list a (non-exhaustive) number of possible channels of dissemination of the objectives of the WYRED Project.

In order to make this document clearer, stakeholders have been divided into two main groups: Global Actors, divided into Youth-led Organizations (22 stakeholders), Research and Digitalization Centres (9 stakeholders) and National Actors, divided, according to their country of origin, into Italy (13 stakeholders), Israel (7 stakeholders), Austria (9 stakeholders), UK (14 stakeholders) and Turkey (9 stakeholders).

The total amount of relevant actors addressing the same target groups and issue is 83 (31 Global Stakeholders and 52 National Stakeholders).

Stakeholders mapping will be the basis to identify the synergies with variety of actors at any level – global, European and national and their work on issues related either to digital society or their work with young people and children using different methodologies to have their voices heard and have them involved in the decision-making processes through consultations or any other participatory process.

Example of stakeholder mapping:

- **The European Youth Forum (from Youth Forum Jeunesse, YFJ)**

<http://www.youthforum.org/> is the platform of the national youth councils and international non-governmental youth organisations in Europe. It strives for youth rights in international institutions such as the European Union, the Council of Europe and the United Nations, focusing its work on European youth policy matters, whilst through engagement on the global level it is enhancing the capacities of its members and promoting global interdependence. In its daily work the European Youth Forum represents the views and opinions of youth organisations in all relevant policy areas and promotes the cross-sectoral nature of youth policy towards a variety of institutional actors. The principles of equality and sustainable development are mainstreamed in the work of the European Youth Forum.

Why should we be interested? The five key priorities in 2018 are going to be: 1) Youth Rights; 2) Strong Youth Organisations; 3) Sustainable Development; 4) Social & Economic Inclusion; 5) Participation. Reports, Policy Papers and other publications that might be useful to our project.

Contact Manuel - manuel.gil@youthforum.org

Partner responsible to contact:

YEU

- **The UNICEF Voices of Youth**

VOY was founded in 1995 as UNICEF's online place for young people to learn more about issues affecting their world. Today, VOY is a vibrant community of youth bloggers from all over the world, offering inspiring, original insight and opinion on a variety of topics. Everyone is welcome to write, film, comment and engage in discussions. <http://www.voicesofyouth.org/>

Why should we be interested? Halfway between a blog and an interactive platform, it successfully engages children and young people's voices in a constructive dialogue around digital technologies.

VOY is a youth led blog. Their topics are similar to the WYRED topics like education, environment, violence, employment, culture, technology ,...

The platform offers tools for participants to advise them in blogging for newcomers and advanced bloggers (shared at the platform: and creating a film (plan it, film it, cut it, share it - Videos on YouTube)

Could be used either to link to related discussions to WYRED threads or - if agreed - be fed by participants' blog post. And: VOY welcomes partnerships with other youth-focused websites, communities and organizations. "E-mail to info@voicesofyouth.org for more information on how you can partner with Voices of Youth.

Contact Ilaria Favero

Detailed results of stakeholder mapping are enlisted in the Valorisation report -2nd year prepared by Consortium partner, Oxfam.

3. WYRED Narrative - approaching young people

WYRED Consortium has developed new narrative for WYRED project with an aim to better approach young people as WYRED's most important stakeholders.

The most important part of developing it was to support young people of all backgrounds, education levels and ages to understand what is the added value for them to take part in WYRED. The most common question we are getting from young people is: what can I do in WYRED? How can I join?

As Consortium we have tried to explain and address these questions in simple and "to the point" language with no potentially unknown terminology that would push young people away thinking that they are not educated or informed enough to take part in discussions while believing that their voice doesn't matter.

Consortium has changed the approach towards young people but also emphasised the importance of continuously consulting young people regarding project related activities.

WHAT CAN YOU EXPECT FROM PARTICIPATING IN WYRED?

You can expect to make a difference. When you participate in WYRED we ensure that your views are heard, and listened to, by the people who make decisions. Both the opinions you express, and the results of your WYRED projects are shared with the right people so that your views can make a difference.

You can expect to meet and work with others from other countries. In our online conversations you can talk to others who are interested in the same issues as you are, and if you like you can work on the same project with them, national and internationally.

You can expect to be in charge. In WYRED you choose what to work on, it is your project your voice, and your decision. We can help, we can suggest how to approach it, and still it is your project and you decide.

You can expect to express your opinion freely. No-one is judging, no-one has specific expectations, and there are no right answers. WYRED is your platform from which to tell the world what you think, in a free, safe space.

You can expect to improve your understanding of the digital world. In WYRED you go beyond simply expressing a like or dislike, or your basic opinion. You actually explore the issues that matter to you and share it with peers.

You can expect to explore in depth. WYRED is a space in which you have the opportunity to go deeper in to a subject that interests you and find out what is really going on, as opposed to what the media or others are telling you. It is a chance to explore in your own way!

You can expect to have a good time. WYRED involves work, and concentration, but most of the people who have participated so far say they have found it interesting and enjoyable, and they have valued the chance to make a difference.

SO WHAT DOES IT INVOLVE?

FIRST, WE TALK. In groups we discuss the digital world, what we value about it, what we think doesn't work, how we feel about the issues. Our opinions are captured, and WYRED helps to communicate them to the world. We may participate in wider conversations on the WYRED platform. As we talk, we notice things that we could explore more, these are our questions.

SECOND, WE TAKE ACTION, we take our questions and explore them in more depth, on our own, in groups, or with people in other countries. You can design your own project and the WYRED team can help with the process. Then you record our results and share them in the WYRED community in any way you choose. You can be as creative as you like!

LASTLY, WE SHARE OUR RESULTS. We look at what we have found out and decide what we want to share, what we feel is the most important message for people to hear, especially those in power.

We share first on the WYRED platform, where we might find similar projects and results, and then we share more widely, supported by the WYRED team and its network. This might lead to other activities, some participants have spoken at conferences, and even in Parliament, about the work. It might also lead to further exploration.

4. Delphi2 study

The main objective of the Delphi study in WYRED (Hauptman & Soffer, 2017; Rodríguez-Conde, García- Holgado, Zangrando, & García-Peñalvo, 2018) was to identify and prioritize key areas of interest for young persons (to be explored further in the subsequent activities of the project), and to provide additional insights regarding the involvement of young people in decision making related to their concerns, attitudes and perceptions.

The Delphi method is widely used in different areas, for the elicitation of experts' opinions on a certain subject, by means of an iterative anonymous group interaction. It involves repeated (multi-round) polling of individuals, in each round feeding back anonymized responses from earlier rounds. The idea is that such a process allows for better judgements to be made without undue influence from certain "dominant" individuals.

The second WYRED Delphi questionnaire (Hauptman et al., 2018) consisted of two parts: in the first part the respondents were requested to prioritize issues of concern for young people by their importance, based on a closed list of issues that emerged from the previous Delphi study.

In the second part, 3-4 alternative future-oriented statements ("mini-scenarios") were presented for each of seven selected issues of concern for young people. The young respondents were requested to assess the likelihood of each mini-scenario, to rate the impact of the issue (on the society and on the individual), and to propose (in free text) how young people and decision makers should cope with each issue.

The survey was run in January-March 2018. The questionnaires were accessible online, in six languages according to the WYRED partner countries: English, Spanish, German, Italian, Hebrew and Turkish. Potential participants were invited via-email by the respective partners.

987 young people participated in the Delphi2 survey. 355 participants submitted complete answers to all questions. 632 respondents submitted answers to part of the questions, namely (in most cases) full answers in part A (ranking of important issues) plus responses to some of the alternative scenarios in part B.

Detailed description, results and analysis of the Delphi are presented in a separate WYRED report titled: "WYRED Second Delphi Study" dated July 2018.

5. Recommendations

In order to have even higher participation of stakeholders and seeing the added value of being part of WYRED processes, main recommendations are:

- It is important not to forget that young people and children are very diverse and heterogeneous group of different backgrounds (religion, culture, orientation), age (cultural background affects defining the age of the young – both in lower and higher age limit), educational and social status or even political affiliation. WYRED can't represent whole generations or take into consideration only the needs or practices of one while risking neglecting the other. Instead, WYRED needs to stay open for all the opinions and thoughts of young people from various backgrounds.
- Terminology of WYRED project needs to be adjusted to young people and this should always be kept in mind – complex terms and phrases can be more intimidating than appealing if we are aiming at approaching young people and children with fewer opportunities.
- Young people should be encouraged to participate and kept being reminded that their voice matters even if they use simpler phrases or their needs seem to be simple and not “life changing”. WYRED Consortium is using different ways to interact with young people and children and gives them opportunity to express their thoughts through audio, video and any other kind of materials.
- WYRED process and platform need to be seen and understood by young people and children as safe spaces in which there are no good or bad answers but constant brainstorming and exchange of ideas and thoughts on topics of their interest.
- Keep young people and children informed about the opportunities: using the platform or creating opportunities to interact with decision and policy makers. WYRED Consortium has additional opportunities to put young people in touch with decision makers by mapping events in which young people could take part, such as European Youth Event, especially in the light of upcoming EU Elections in May 2019.

6. Conclusions

WYRED Consortium has clearly identified stakeholders to approach and narrative to communicate. Terminology used in building the network is different and it depends if Consortium is communicating to young people and children or other civil society actors.

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This is especially important because there is a clear increase of young people's interest in WYRED activities due to change of design (Manifesto), process of consultations, direct involvement in events where young people can interact with decision makers and other young people (European Youth Event).

Further networking will probably go in two parallel tracks while still promoting the same idea and narrative of WYRED project:

- amplify youth voices
- strengthen youth views through youth-led research
- connect youth with decision-makers
- broaden understanding of the digital society
- make youth perspectives matter

Important period in showing that young people's voices matter and encouraging them to exercise their political rights is coming with EU Elections 2019 and WYRED Consortium has an excellent opportunity to put in touch young people and children with decision and policy makers to affect EU agendas and policies and ensure youth issues mainstreaming on EU level.

7. Annexes to the D.4.4 – Networking report

Annex 1 - Manifesto – full version

Annex 2 - Manifesto – short version

8. References

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